

CUSTOMER SEGMENTATION THROUGH PAYMENT PATTERNS AND BEHAVIORAL INSIGHTS

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Abstract

Customer segmentation is an important part of businesses group their clients based on their insights and characteristics. This study focuses on solving a company's challenge in segmenting customers by analyzing real-time payment data. Machine learning techniques are used to improve the accuracy and effectiveness of segmentation. A comparison of classification methods is done to distinguish between premium and standard customers using two-dimensional payment information. Among these, the K-Means clustering algorithm is applied to recognize patterns and group customers based on their purchasing behavior. The model is trained on retail business datasets to ensure scalability and accuracy in customer segmentation. The results show that machine learning makes segmentation faster and more efficient than traditional manual methods. This approach helps businesses make better decisions and create strategies that meet the needs of different customer groups.

This data-driven approach enables businesses to make informed decisions and develop customized strategies to meet the specific demands of different customer segments.

Keywords:

Customer Relationship Management (CRM), Marketing strategies, Machine Learning (ML), Classification methods, K-means clustering

1. Introduction

This project groups customers based on shared characteristics such as age, location, behavior, or spending habits. This process helps businesses understand their customer base, enabling personalized marketing strategies and informed decisions about product development and engagement. Common segmentation types include geographical segmentation, which organizes customers by location, and demographic segmentation, which classifies customers by traits like age, gender, or income. Behavioral segmentation analyzes past actions, such as purchase patterns or brand preferences, to predict future behavior. Traditional segmentation methods are often manual, time consuming, and lack precision due to reliance on predefined assumptions and limited data analysis. Machine learning (ML) offers a robust alternative by automating segmentation and uncovering deeper patterns within customer data. Algorithms like k-means clustering and DBSCAN analyze large datasets to identify meaningful customer groups, making the process more efficient and adaptable to evolving

trends. This project leverages ML-based clustering algorithms to group customers into meaningful segments, particularly distinguishing premium customers from standard ones using real payment data. The approach enhances accuracy, scalability, and adaptability, allowing businesses to design targeted marketing campaigns, improve resource allocation, and increase customer satisfaction in a competitive market.

1.1 Scope of Project

The scope of this project involves developing and applying machine learning techniques for customer segmentation based on payment patterns and behavioral insights. It includes gathering and preprocessing customer payment data to identify key features such as spending habits, transaction frequency, and payment methods. Various machine learning algorithms, including k-means clustering and other clustering techniques, will be implemented and compared to create meaningful customer segments. The segmented groups will be analyzed to uncover patterns and trends that can inform targeted marketing and customer engagement strategies. The project also focuses on fine-tuning machine learning models to ensure optimal performance, scalability, and adaptability to evolving customer behaviors. Businesses will be provided with actionable insights, such as identifying premium customers or high-value groups, to enhance marketing strategies and resource allocation. Additionally, a user-friendly interface will be developed to visualize segmentation results, enabling businesses to interpret and apply the insights effectively.

2. Literature Survey

The literature review in this paper emphasizes the importance of customer segmentation. Singh and Agarwal aimed to personalize mobile payment offers by segmenting users based on their behavior with digital wallets, identifying patterns in user interactions. However, they noted limitations like the potential for outdated patterns and concerns about user

privacy. They suggested that dynamic model updates could help businesses stay competitive in a rapidly evolving market. Althoff and Jurasky explored the use of DL techniques to analyze intricate patterns in online payment transactions for customer segmentation. While deep learning(DL) models showed promise in uncovering complex relationships, challenges such as high computational costs, model complexity, and privacy concerns were highlighted. Yang and Zhang discussed the challenges faced by real-time customer segmentation models, particularly in adapting to dynamic changes in payment behavior, handling large data volumes, and achieving high segmentation accuracy. Zhang and Liu proposed a DL approach based on purchase history data to identify hidden patterns in customer behavior, allowing for more accurate segmentation. However, they cautioned against the risk of overfitting and the need for extensive labeled data. Sharma and Roy focused on using machine learning for real-time customer segmentation in ecommerce, aiming to improve customer experiences by providing tailored offers. Their study pointed out the challenges of high computational costs and difficulties in processing large amounts of live-streaming data efficiently

3. Existing System

Traditional customer segmentation methods often depend on manual processes or simple statistical techniques, which come with various limitations. Manual segmentation can be subjective and prone to human bias, leading to inaccurate customer groupings. Furthermore, basic statistical methods may not fully leverage the available data, potentially missing valuable insights. Finally, traditional methods may not adapt well to evolving customer behavior and market dynamics, limiting their effectiveness in the long term.

4. Proposed System

The proposed system overcomes the drawbacks of traditional customer segmentation by utilizing machine learning, particularly the K-Means clustering algorithm. It processes real customer data, emphasizing payment and purchase patterns, to categorize customers into distinct groups. Additionally, the system is flexible and can retrain with new data to maintain accurate and updated segmentation. The Elbow Method is used to determine the optimal number of clusters. The system is adaptable, capable of retraining with new data to ensure up-to-date segments. It is scalable and incorporates various customer data types for comprehensive analysis. This enables more effective targeting of marketing and sales efforts, leading to increased customer satisfaction and retention. The system also integrates visualizations, such as 3D scatter plots, to provide a clear visual representation of customer segments. It aims to enhance customer segmentation by leveraging machine learning techniques to analyze and classify customers into premium and standard categories. Unlike traditional manual methods, which are time-consuming and often lack precision, the proposed approach utilizes the K-means clustering algorithm to identify patterns and group customers based on their payment behaviours. This system processes real customer data to uncover meaningful insights, enabling more effective marketing strategies and decision-making. By automating segmentation with machine learning, the system ensures scalability, retraining ease, and improved accuracy, making it adaptable to evolving customer data and trends. Additionally, the system incorporates advanced methodologies, including the Elbow Method to determine the optimal number of clusters, and integrates tools like Google Colab for seamless implementation. This approach not only saves time but also provides businesses with a robust framework to understand and address customer needs dynamically.

Fig 1: Data Flow of Model

5. Methodology

5.1 Data Gathering : This dataset for this study was obtained from online retail sources and includes key details such as transaction amounts, payment frequencies, payment methods, and customer demographics.

Dealing with Incomplete Data:

To manage missing entries in the dataset, various statistical imputation methods were applied. For numerical features, missing values were filled using either the **mean** or **median**, depending on the distribution of the data. For categorical fields, the **most frequent category (mode)** was used to replace missing values. In cases where data records had a substantial amount of missing information, they were **excluded** from the analysis to preserve the overall integrity and reliability of the dataset.

Feature Selection: Important features such as transaction frequency, average spending, payment methods, and customer demographics were selected to gain insights into payment behavior and improve segmentation accuracy.

Data Encoding: Categorical variables, including payment methods and customer locations, were transformed into numerical representations using label encoding and one-hot encoding to ensure compatibility with machine learning models.

Normalization and Standardization: Numerical features, such as transaction amounts and frequencies, were scaled to a uniform range (e.g., 0 to 1) to enhance consistency and improve the effectiveness of clustering algorithms.

Fig 2: Customer Segmentation flow

5.2 Exploratory Data Analysis

Correlation Analysis: Identify correlations between features such as transaction frequency, average spending, and payment methods using techniques like correlation matrices. Correlation analysis was chosen to understand relationships between variables, providing insights into how certain behaviors influence segmentation outcomes.

Feature Importance: Rank features by importance using methods such as feature importance scores from Random Forest or mutual information. This helps determine which factors, like spending patterns or payment methods, contribute most significantly to meaningful customer segmentation.

5.3 Model Building and Training

In this phase, various machine learning models are built, trained, and evaluated to achieve effective customer segmentation.

Train-Test Split: The dataset is divided into training and testing sets, typically with 80% used for training and 20% for testing.

Model Selection: Several clustering algorithms are trained to analyze customer segmentation, including:

- **K-Means Clustering**
- **DBSCAN (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise)**

- **Hierarchical Clustering**
- **Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM)**
- **Agglomerative Clustering**

5.4 Model Evaluation

To assess the clustering models, various evaluation metrics are used. Clustering, an unsupervised learning technique, groups similar data points into clusters. The performance of the model is analyzed based on its ability to distinguish clear customer segments.

Key evaluation metrics include:

- **Silhouette Score:** Measures how well data points fit within their assigned clusters compared to other clusters.
- **Davies-Bouldin Index:** Evaluates the average similarity ratio between each cluster and other clusters.
- **Adjusted Rand Index:** Compares the clustering results with ground truth labels or external benchmarks to measure consistency.
- **Confusion Matrix:** Although not typically used for unsupervised models, it can still help evaluate segment assignments by comparing them with predefined customer categories when available.

6. Applying Clustering Algorithms and Obtaining Results

K-Means clustering is applied to group customers based on their payment behavior. Essential features extracted from customer data include **average transaction value, purchase frequency, preferred payment methods, and time intervals between purchases**. The **Elbow Method** is used to determine the optimal number of clusters by identifying the point where increasing clusters no longer significantly reduce within-cluster variance. K-Means then categorizes customers into **k** segments based on similarities in their payment behavior. Customers with **similar spending habits, transaction frequencies, and payment preferences** are grouped together, enabling businesses to implement targeted marketing strategies and improve customer engagement.

This study explores customer segmentation using both **K-Means and DBSCAN clustering algorithms**. K-Means divides customers into a **predefined number of clusters (K)** by minimizing the within-cluster sum of squares.

In contrast, **DBSCAN** identifies clusters based on data point density, making it effective for detecting clusters of different shapes and sizes. Applying these algorithms to customer data, including **payment behavior, purchase history, and relevant attributes**, helps in identifying distinct customer segments with unique characteristics. These segments allow businesses to **tailor marketing strategies, enhance customer retention, and improve overall business performance**.

6.1 Choosing the Optimal Cluster Count: The Elbow Approach

One widely adopted strategy for identifying the most suitable number of clusters in a K-Means model is the **Elbow Approach**. This method is centered on evaluating the **Within-Cluster Sum of Squares (WCSS)**, a metric that quantifies the compactness of clusters by measuring the total variance within each cluster. The primary objective is to determine the point at which increasing the number of clusters yields

diminishing returns in terms of variance reduction.

In this approach, the K-Means algorithm is executed repeatedly across a range of values for k (the number of clusters). For each iteration, the WCSS is calculated and plotted against k . Initially, as k increases, the WCSS drops rapidly, indicating more precise clustering. However, beyond a certain point, the rate of improvement slows considerably. This inflection point, where the rate of decrease in WCSS sharply changes, is referred to as the "**elbow**", and it suggests the ideal number of clusters.

It's important to note that identifying this elbow is not always straightforward—it can sometimes be ambiguous, especially when

bent. Additionally, this method assumes the data is appropriate for K-Means clustering, which works best with spherical and evenly sized clusters.

Figure 3: Elbow Plot

To support this process, a function (e.g., `evaluate_clusters`) is typically implemented to run the K-Means algorithm over a specified range of cluster values and generate the WCSS plot. This visualization helps in determining the point where adding more clusters offers marginal gains.

Based on our analysis, the elbow appears to occur around $k = 5$, indicating that five clusters may provide an optimal balance between model complexity and accuracy.

the curve is smooth rather than sharply

6.2 Applying the K-Means Algorithm

K-Means is a popular algorithm for solving clustering tasks, especially useful in applications such as **customer segmentation**. It is a form of **unsupervised learning**, meaning it identifies inherent structures in data without using predefined labels.

What is Unsupervised Learning?

Unsupervised learning differs significantly from supervised learning. While supervised algorithms rely on labeled data to make predictions or classifications, unsupervised techniques like clustering aim to uncover hidden patterns or groupings in data without

any prior knowledge of class labels. These methods group data points based on similarity measures such as Euclidean distance.

Clustering, a core type of unsupervised learning, groups similar data items into clusters, making it possible to detect natural divisions in a dataset. K-Means, in particular, works by initializing cluster centers and iteratively refining them so that the sum of distances between each point and its assigned cluster center is minimized.

This algorithm is especially advantageous in scenarios where we need to explore the structure of data, segment populations, or reduce dimensionality for visualization.

6.1 Visualizing customer segments

To better understand the customer segments identified by the K-Means algorithm, we create an interactive 3D visualization using Plotly Express. This approach helps in exploring the distribution of different customer groups in a visually engaging manner.

First, a new column is added to the dataset to indicate each customer's assigned cluster.

Next, a 3D scatter plot is generated using Plotly Express, where each point represents a customer. The points are color-coded based on their respective cluster assignments, making it easy to distinguish different customer groups. This visualization provides valuable insights into how customers are grouped and the relationships between different segments.

Results:

Figure 4: clusters of customers

This scatter plot likely depicts customer segmentation based on features such as Age (X-axis) and Spending Score (Y-axis). Different colors represent distinct clusters identified by your clustering algorithm (e.g., K-Means). Customers are grouped into clusters based on their similarity.

Red markers likely indicate the centroids of each cluster. This clustering is useful for segmenting customers to design targeted marketing strategies or identify spending patterns.

6.2 Applying the DBSCAN Algorithm

Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise is a clustering algorithm that identifies groups of data points based on their density. Instead of relying on a fixed number of clusters, DBSCAN detects dense regions in the feature space—such as customer attributes like purchase frequency, transaction value, and payment methods—while also recognizing and isolating outliers.

By applying DBSCAN to customer data, we can uncover natural customer segments based on density, leading to more precise and

insightful groupings without the need to predefine the number of clusters.

Results:

Figure5: Demonstrates the clustering output from the DBSCAN

DBSCAN: Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise

The **DBSCAN algorithm** clusters data points based on their density, making it effective for identifying **irregularly shaped clusters** and detecting **outliers**. In a visual representation, different colors are used to distinguish clusters, while black points indicate noise—data points that do not belong to any cluster.

In this case, the estimated number of clusters is **3**, with **18 noise points** (black dots). DBSCAN also evaluates cluster **purity**, meaning how well data points within a cluster share common characteristics. A purity score close to **1** suggests that the clusters are highly homogeneous, ensuring meaningful segmentation.

7. Conclusion

This analysis investigates the use of **K-Means** and **DBSCAN** as clustering algorithms for

segmenting customers into distinct groups. Both approaches are capable of identifying customer segments based on behavioral similarities; however, **DBSCAN** (Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) provides a unique benefit—it can identify **anomalous or outlier customers**, such as those exhibiting unusual purchasing patterns.

This feature gives DBSCAN an edge in applications that require personalized marketing, as it can single out non-typical consumers who may benefit from custom-tailored offers or services. As a result, businesses can gain deeper insights and design more effective engagement strategies, potentially increasing both customer satisfaction and profitability.

The evaluation underscores the strength of **density-based clustering** in capturing meaningful groupings without needing to specify the number of clusters in advance. Unlike K-Means, which demands a predetermined cluster count, DBSCAN naturally adapts to the underlying data structure and uncovers patterns that might otherwise go unnoticed.

Furthermore, the study points toward future opportunities, such as incorporating **Neural Networks** or testing alternative clustering frameworks across varied datasets. These advanced approaches could enhance the precision of customer segmentation and further optimize decision-making in marketing and business strategy.

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